

The importance of transverse second-order wave loads, a case study of a bulk carrier with wing sails in regular waves

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Abstract. The seakeeping behavior of a bulk carrier with four wing sails is investigated in regular waves. A time-domain simulation framework, which combines seakeeping and maneuvering, is applied in the study. The simulation framework is validated against experimental data, without sails, with reasonable agreement. In calm water with wind from the side, the sails contribute with 48% of the total thrust. Simulations in head wave conditions show a negligible effect of the sails on wave induced motions and added power. In beam sea, the amplitude of the roll resonance is reduced by the sails, while only minor differences are seen for other wave periods. However, the added power in waves for short wave periods, is higher with sails compared to without. This is caused by high drift angles, which reduce the angle of attack and the thrust from the sails. The high drift angles were caused by the mean second-order yaw moment, and was also observed for simulations without sails. This emphasize the importance of also including transverse second-order wave loads in predictions, and not only the added resistance in waves.

Key words: *Wind assisted propulsion, Seakeeping, Added thrust, Added Power, Second-order wave loads, SOBC-1*

1. Introduction

Wind assisted propulsion is established as one of the most low hanging fruits to reduce fuel consumption and emission of green house gases from merchant ships. At the end of 2024 over 45 merchant ships had installed sails, and market forecasts predict a rapid increase of installations the coming years. Several studies indicate significant savings from wind assisted ships, e.g. [1] predicted 30% for a tanker and 14% for a RoRo vessel, operational data in [2] indicated 25-50% reduction in fuel consumption over a 24h period. In addition to reduced fuel consumption, ship owners also reports improved seakeeping behavior. Increased roll damping is mentioned, but reduced added resistance and increased operability are also reported. However, there are only a limited number of studies that have investigated these phenomena. [3] and [4] are examples of studies that indicate that especially wing sails can have a significant effect on the wave induced motions. More recently, experimental studies in [5] show reduction in roll for a cruise ship. A reduction in the yaw RAO was also observed. However, there is still uncertainty in performance predictions, and benchmark studies show a significant scatter in predictions [6].

The standard methodology to predict performance of wind assisted ships today is steady state route studies, where polar plots are obtained from power prediction programs (ppp). However, there is large variation of which effects that are included in different tools, and which fidelity that is used for different physical phenomena. The specialist Committee on Wind Powered and Wind assisted Ships in the International Towing Tank Conference (ITTC) has published a Recommended Procedure of Predicting the Power Saving of Wind Powered Ships [7]. The guideline is structured into different level of accuracy, referred to as Level 0 to Level 4, with increasing accuracy for increasing Level. The application of the different Levels are intended for different phases in the design process, where different accuracy is required. For example, for Level 0 and 1, only 1 degree of freedom is included (surge), and added resistance in waves is neglected. The hydrodynamic effects that should be modeled with high accuracy for Level 3 and 4 are: ship resistance,

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ship added resistance in waves, propeller efficiency, propulsive coefficients, hydrodynamic effects of side force, and parasitic resistance from added weight etc. However, it is worth to note that slowly varying second-order sway force and yaw moment are not mentioned in the guideline. Both sails and waves can contribute with significant transverse loads. Moreover, the added resistance due to rudder and drift angles is non-linear. Hence, neglecting the transverse wave loads could lead to non-conservative predictions.

In the present work, a time-domain simulation framework is presented for simulation of maneuvering and seakeeping of wind assisted ships. The framework is first validated against experimental data, without sails. Next, seakeeping behavior of the SINTEF Ocean Bulk carrier (SOBC-1) is investigated with and without sails. Wave induced motions, added thrust, and added power are investigated in head waves and beam waves.

2. Simulation Setup

2.1. Hydrodynamic model

The simulations in this paper are conducted with SINTEF Ocean's Vessel Simulator (VeSim), recent developments in VeSim are presented in [8]. This is a simulation framework that unifies vessel hydrodynamics formulation to handle seakeeping and maneuvering consistently. In addition to hull loads and propulsor loads, environmental loads (wind, wave, current), engines, and control systems can also be modeled. Several maneuvering models are implemented in VeSim, which can use input from different sources, e.g. CFD or model tests. However, the maneuvering coefficients in the present work are calculated with SINTEF Ocean's tool Hullvisc, which utilize theoretical methods based on slender body theory and a sophisticated cross-flow drag method, with some empirical corrections.

In the present study, calm water resistance curve, propeller open water curve, and propulsion coefficients are obtained from experiments. Wave induced motions, forces and moments (first- and second-order) are calculated by SINTEF Ocean's tool VERES, which is a strip theory code based on potential flow theory. VERES calculate coefficients in frequency plane, which VeSim incorporates in time-domain with retardation functions.

2.2. Aerodynamic model

A library based on dynamic lifting line theory is used to calculate the aerodynamic loads. The methodology is described in [9], and it is also applied in the studies presented in [10]. The lifting line library is validated against CFD results, with good agreement. The lifting line library is coupled with the hydrodynamic model, and ship motions in 5 degrees of freedom (heave motion is neglected in the aerodynamic calculations) are input to the aerodynamic model. In the present study, no control system is used to control the wing sails, i.e. the wing angles are constant during a simulation.

2.3. Case ship

The SINTEF Ocean Bulk Carrier 1 (SOBC-1) is used as case ship in this study. The hull was developed by SINTEF Ocean together with industry partners as a demonstrator for new technology. The main dimensions were selected to be representative of the class of medium size, single screw bulk carrier. The ship geometry is open and it is used in several ongoing research projects. The main particulars can be found in Table 1. The hull geometry and available benchmark data can be downloaded from [11].

For the present case study the ship is equipped with four generic wing sails. The height and width of the sails are 42 m and 14 m respectively. They are equally distributed along the center line, where the aft most sail is placed 28 m ahead of AP. There could be other placement that is more appropriate than the present arrangement. Moreover, practical challenges, e.g. visibility or cranes, are not considered. It is considered that the generic hull and sail arrangement are satisfactory for the present study.

Table 1. Main particulars of SOBC-1 at design waterline

Length overall, LOA	200 m
Length betw. perp., LPP	190 m
Length on waterline, LWL	196.942 m
Breadth molded, B	32.295 m
Breadth waterline, BWL	32.201 m
Draught at FP/AP and LPP/2, T	11.000 m
Bilge radius	2 m
Wetted surface	8485.24 m ²
Wetted surf. of transom stern AT	92.12 m ²
Volume displacement ∇	48957 m ³
Prismatic coefficient (based on LPP), C_p	0.7308
Block coefficient (based on LWL), C_{BLW}	0.7018
Propeller diameter, D	6.75 m
Pitch ratio at $r/R = 0.7$, $P/D_{0.7}$	0.970
Blade area ratio, A_E/A_0	0.483
Number of blades, Z	4
Chord/Diameter ratio, $c/D_{0.7R}$	0.3209
Thickness/Diameter ratio, $t/D_{0.7R}$	0.0324
Hub diameter ratio, d/D	0.252
Number of wing sails	4
Wing height, H	42 m
Wing width, w	14 m

3. Validation

SOBC-1 has been used in several benchmark studies and different kind of experimental results exists. Prior to initiating case studies with wind assisted propulsion, the numerical model, without sail, is compared to relevant experimental results. In Figures 1.-2., Heave RAOs, Pitch RAOs, and Added resistance in head waves are compared to experimental values. All comparisons are conducted at 12 knots. In the simulations, a speed controller and autopilot are used to control propeller rpm and rudder angle. The simulations are done in time-domain. Hence, the simulations need some time to stabilize at the correct speed and heading. A steady time-window at the end of the simulations are used to extract RAOs and added resistance values. The experiments were conducted in SINTEF Ocean's towing tank with a 1:32.000 scale model, where the model was towed in a hybrid test setup replicating a soft mooring system [12].

The overall trends are well represented by the numerical simulation model. For the heave RAO, the simulations slightly over-predict the peak values, while for shorter wave length the simulations are slightly below the experimental values. For Pitch, the simulations slightly under-predict the peak, while good agreement is seen for other wave lengths. The peak value of added resistance is significantly under-predicted in the simulations compared to experiments, while for other wave lengths the accuracy is reasonable good.

Heading, rudder angle, and trajectory, from a Zig-Zag 10/10 maneuver, with initial velocity 12 knots, are presented in Figure 3.. The experimental results are obtained from model tests in SINTEF Ocean's Ocean Basin with a free running model at 1:32.000 scale [13]. The length and width of the basin is 80x50 m, and the water depth can be adjusted between 0 and 10 m. Even though the basin is relatively large, it was not possible to complete the Zig-Zag 10/10 maneuver at 12 knots. Only the first overshoot angle was captured by the experiments. However, good agreement between simulations and experiments is obtained.

Some minor deviations are found between the numerical model and the simulations. However, the accuracy is reasonable good and the overall trends are well represented. It is therefore considered that the hydrodynamic model is accurate enough to proceed with case studies with sails.

Figure 1. Comparison of RAOs obtained from time-domain simulations with experimental results in Head sea, 12 knots. Right: Heave RAO. Left: Pitch RAO

Figure 2. Comparison of added resistance in waves (Raw) obtained from time-domain simulations with experimental results. Head sea, 12 knots.

4. Results

4.1. Calm Water

Simulations in calm water were conducted as a reference to simulations in waves. Mean values for some selected quantities are presented in Table 2. for two different True Wind Directions (TWD). Results without sails are compared to simulations with sails with TWD=30° and TWD=90°, True Wind Speed (TWS) was 10 m/s for both scenarios. For TWD=30°, the fraction of thrust from the sails is 13.01% and the propeller power is reduced by 12.8%, while for TWD=90° the sails produce 48.08% of the thrust and the propeller power is reduced by 47.97%. Moderate Heel and Drift angles were observed, and the steady rudder angle was below 3.47° for both conditions.

Figure 3. Comparison of a Zig-Zag 10/10 maneuver in calm water, initial velocity 12 knots. Top: Heading and rudder angle. Bottom: Trajectory.

Table 2. Mean values from simulations with and without sails in calm water

	No Sails	TWD = 30°	TWD = 90°
U [knots]	12	12	12
Propeller Thrust [kN]	312.47	272.39	162.58
Sail Thrust [kN]	-	40.73	150.57
Fraction of Thrust from Sails	-	13.01%	48.08 %
Propeller Power [kW]	2764.41	2420.11	1446.74
Heel Angle [deg]	0	0.50	0.30
Drift Angle [deg]	0	-1.08	-0.61
Rudder Angle [deg]	-0.16	-3.47	-2.5
Apparent wind direction [deg]	-	18.87	58.49
Angle of Attack 1 [deg]	-	8.69	11.54
Angle of Attack 2 [deg]	-	5.79	10.53
Angle of Attack 3 [deg]	-	5.16	10.14
Angle of Attack 4 [deg]	-	5.23	10.14

4.2. Regular Waves

The following section presents results from simulations with and without sails in regular waves. An autopilot is used to control the rudder to keep the heading, and a speed controller is applied to adjust the propeller rpm to keep a velocity of 12 knots. No particular focus is given to tuning and optimization of the controllers. However, the same control parameters are used for simulations with and without sails. For all simulations in regular waves the wave height was kept constant at 2.0 m.

For simulations with sails, TWS=10 m/s for all simulations, while TWD is varied. Moreover, the wing angles for the sail are kept constant for a given wind direction (TWD), and are identical as the angles used in the calm water simulations. Hence, no control systems is applied to control the wing angles during a simulation.

Comparisons of simulations with and without sails, in head waves, are presented in Figures 4.-5.. The heave and pitch RAOs in Figure 4. are identical with and without sails. Added thrust (T_{add}) and added

power (P_{add}) are given in Figure 5.. These quantities are defined as:

$$T_{add} = T_{waves} - T_{calm} \quad (1)$$

$$P_{add} = P_{waves} - P_{calm} \quad (2)$$

Where T_{calm} and T_{waves} are the total thrust in calm water and waves respectively, while P_{calm} and P_{waves} represent the propeller power in calm water and waves. For simulations with sails, the thrust is the sum of propeller thrust and thrust from sail. Added thrust and power without sails are calculated based on a calm water reference run without sails, while with sails the calm water reference run is with sails. It is seen that the differences in added thrust and added power with and without sails in head waves are negligible. It is important to emphasize that even though the difference in added thrust and added power is negligible for these conditions, the power consumption with sails is still significant lower than without.

Figure 4. Comparison of RAOs in Heave and Pitch in Head Waves. Velocity 12 knots. For simulations with sails, TWD=30°. Left: Heave RAO. Right: Pitch RAO.

Figure 5. Comparison of Added thrust and Added propeller power in Head Waves. Velocity 12 knots. For simulations with sails, TWD=30°. Left: Added thrust. Right: Added propeller power.

RAOs in heave and roll, in beam sea, are presented in Figure 6.. The differences in the heave RAO are negligible. For roll, the peak value is significant lower with sails compared to without, while for other wave periods there are only minor deviations.

Added thrust and added power, in beam sea are presented in Figure 7.. At wave period 9 s, the added thrust is 14.7% higher with sails, while for other wave periods the difference in added thrust is minor for simulations with and without sails. Hence, the reduction in the roll RAO at the resonance peak (T=18 s), doesn't contribute significantly to a reduction in added thrust.

For added power at long wave periods, only minor differences are observed. However, for shorter wave periods, 10 s and below, the added power is significantly higher with sails than without. At wave period 10 s, the added power with sails is 53.7% higher than with sails. This increase is significantly higher than the increase in added thrust.

Figure 6. Comparison of RAOs in Heave and Roll in Beam Waves. Velocity 12 knots. For simulations with sails, TWD=90°. Left: Heave RAO. Right: Roll RAO.

Figure 7. Comparison of Added thrust and Added propeller power in Beam Waves. Velocity 12 knots. For simulations with sails, TWD=90°. Left: Added thrust. Right: Added propeller power.

To better understand why the increase in added power is significantly higher than the increase in added thrust, added thrust for the propeller and sails are presented in Figure 8. It is observed that the added thrust from the sails is negative for wave periods below 15 s, which means that the thrust from the sails in these conditions is lower than what it is in calm water. Hence, the required increase in propeller thrust in waves, is higher with sails than without.

The reduction in thrust from the sails in waves compared to calm water is because the wing sails experience a lower angle of attack, which is caused by the ship's drift angle. This is illustrated in Figure 9., where the mean angle of attack (average of the four wings), drift angle, and rudder angle are presented. For most of the wave periods the angle of attack is lower than in calm water, and for the shortest waves the angle of attack is more than 3° lower. The absolute value of the drift angle and rudder angle is highest for the shortest wave period with an increasing trend with wave period, except for a local peak at the roll resonance period. However, the drift angle and rudder angle are significant, even for the simulations without sails. This is probably due to the mean second-order yaw moment from waves. The mean second-order yaw moment in waves is not investigated as thoroughly in the literature as the added resistance. However, there are some experimental studies that show that the mean second-order yaw moment can vary significantly at moderate wave lengths, and the peak can be found at wavelengths around $\lambda/L_{pp}=0.5$, see e.g. [14] and [15].

Figure 8. Added thrust from propeller and sails for a range of regular wave lengths.

The results in Figure 9. reminds us that ships without sails also can experience significant drift angles and rudder angles due to influence of environmental loads. In this case, the loads from the sails amplifies this effect, and the maximum drift angle and rudder angle are 6.16° and 13.26° respectively.

Figure 9. Left: Mean local angle of attack for the four wing sails. Right: Comparison of Drift Angle and Rudder angle with and without sails

As mentioned earlier, no control system is applied to adjust the wing angles during a simulation. It is expected that sail providers have control systems that change the wing angles according to the apparent wind direction (AWD). To investigate sensitivity of added power to angle of attack for the wing sails, simulations in beam sea were rerun, where the angle of attacks were adjusted. The wing angles were adjusted with the difference in angle of attack in calm water and waves. For example, if the mean angle of attack for the four sails were 7° in a given wave condition, all wings were adjusted 3.58° (the mean angle of attack in calm water was 10.58°). In Figure 10., added power and added thrust from simulations with adjusted wing

angles are compared to simulations where the wing angles were kept the same as in calm water. For wave periods 7, 8, and 9 s the added power is slightly lower when the wing angles are adjusted, while for the rest of the wavelengths only minor differences are observed. The same trend can be seen for the added thrust, where the reduction in sail thrust in waves is smaller for the shortest wave lengths when the wing angles are adjusted. However, there is still a negative added sail thrust for short wavelengths, and the added power is higher than without sails. This indicates that the reduction in angle of attack is not the only reason for the increased added power. The added resistance from rudder angles is non-linear, and will probably give a significant contribution to the added power in waves.

Figure 10. Left: Added power in waves, simulations with adjusted wing angles are compared to simulations where the wing angles are the same as in calm water. Right: Added thrust from propeller and sails from simulations where wing angles are adjusted.

5. Conclusion

A simulation framework for combined seakeeping and maneuvering, including wind assisted propulsion is presented. Simulations are compared to existing validation data, without sails, with satisfactory accuracy both for seakeeping and maneuvering. The effect of wing sails on the seakeeping behavior of the SINTEF Ocean Bulk Carrier (SOBC) is investigated in regular waves in head and beam sea conditions. For head waves the sails had a negligible effect on the seakeeping quantities such as wave induced motions, added thrust, and added power. In beam waves, the sails have a negligible effect on the heave RAO, while the amplitude of the roll RAO is damped due to the wing sails. However, the added power in waves is higher with sails than without.

The increase in added power in beam sea with sails, is due to increased rudder angles and a reduction in sail thrust in waves compared to calm water. Hence, the required increase in propeller thrust in waves is higher with sails than without. The reduction in sail thrust is due to lower angles of attack, which is caused by high drift angles. Slowly varying second-order yaw moments from waves is the reason for the high drift angles. Significant drift angles were also observed for simulations without sails. This emphasizes the importance of including all relevant effects in order to achieve reliable predictions. If the second-order yaw moment was neglected, the mean rudder and drift angles would have been under-predicted, which would lead to non-conservative estimates for sail thrust and propeller power. However, the mean second-order transverse wave loads are not investigated as thoroughly in the literature as the added resistance from mean second-order wave force in surge. Due to practical reasons, there are limited experimental data available for the transverse wave loads. Furthermore, existing methodology to calculate wave added resistance does, in general, not take into account drift due to waves. This is a topic that needs further research.

Acknowledgments

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support from the Research Council of Norway granted through NFR project 344295, KSP-S WIND.

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